

DEFINITION OF FIQH SCIENCE AND ITS BRIEF HISTORY

Ro'zmetov Muhammad Mustafo

Teacher of Mir Arab Higher Madrasa

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Annotation. Undoubtedly, the science of jurisprudence is one of the necessary sciences that a Muslim must learn. Because this knowledge includes rulings on the circumstances of a person from birth to death. This article describes popular definitions of this science and its brief history.

Key words: Kufa, jurisprudence, jurist, madhhab, Hanafi, tarif, istelah, fuqaha.

"In the dictionary, the word "Fiqh" means detailed understanding, that is, understanding something down to its subtle parts. In the term of Sharia, "It is said that it is fiqh to extract legal rulings from Shari'i evidence. When we say "shar'i evidence" in this definition, we mainly mean the Holy Qur'an and the Sunnah of our Prophet Muhammad, may God bless him and grant him peace. "Far'i rulings" means the opposite of the original, that is, shahabcha, of minor importance. "And in Shariat, rulings that include prayers and treatment are considered.

The meaning of jurisprudence and how high its importance is indicated by the following verse of the Holy Qur'an in Surah "Tawba":

إِذَا قَوْمُهُمْ وَلِيَنْذِرُوا الدِّينَ فِي لِيَتَفَقَّهُوا طَائِفَةٌ مِنْهُمْ فِرْقَةٌ كُلِّ مَنْ نَفَرَ فَلَوْلَا كَافَّةً لِيَنْفِرُوا الْمُؤْمِنُونَ كَانَ وَمَا
يَحْذَرُونَ لَعَلَّهُمْ إِلَيْهِمْ رَجَعُوا

"Believers do not have to go to battle. Doesn't one category emerge from each of their groups?! Do they not warn them when their people return to them after learning religion (from the Prophet) so that they avoid (sin)?"!

This verse shows that the Islamic society should pay special attention to the training of scholars who have deep knowledge of religious sciences. At the same time, he also emphasizes that the positions and responsibilities of scholars in society are high. Also, the Prophet, may God bless him and grant him peace, praised being a jurist in religion in his hadith as follows:

" The Prophet, may God bless him and grant him peace, said: "Whoever Allah wills good for, He makes him a jurist in religion." "

Derived from the word "Fiqh", the science that ensures the understanding of the rulings of Sharia to the smallest detail is also called "Fiqh". A scientist with such scientific qualifications is called a "faqih".

It can be seen from the above verses and hadiths that striving to understand the teachings of religion is a great happiness for a servant. It is a sign that Allah wills good for him.

If we look at the history of the science of fiqh, we will see that in the earlier period of Islam, the science of fiqh, like tafsir, hadith, usul al-fiqh and other sciences, was not separated as a separate science.

At first, the Makkah Mukarramah contained verses related to belief for thirteen years. Later, after the emigration to Madinah Munawwara, the verses related to Shariah rulings also began to be revealed. The Messenger of Allah, peace and blessings be upon him, used to read and explain all of them to the Muslim community, which had not yet increased much. Almost all of the Muslims at that time were Arabs, they understood the Arabic language well to the smallest detail, they understood and followed the verses of the Holy Qur'an and the hadiths of the Prophet, may God bless him and grant him peace, without any difficulty.

In the age of happiness, if there were any misunderstandings, they would immediately ask the Messenger of Allah, peace and blessings of Allah be upon him, and the Messenger of Allah, peace and blessings of Allah be upon him, would explain the answer to them. At that time, this was the main work of the companions in their simple lives.

Towards the end of the blessed life of the Messenger of Allah, may God bless him and grant him peace, the verses of the Holy Qur'an came to an end. Most of the verses in the next stage were related to jurisprudence.

People of different tribes and countries accepted Islam. The new Muslims faced a huge task of reading and studying the verses that had been revealed for almost twenty-three years, following them, and applying the Sharia rules to their lives. Naturally, the young Companions began to ask their elders, the new Muslims to the old ones, and the ignorant to those who knew. In these works, some companions stood out from others with their knowledge and resourcefulness. The companions of our scholars who are famous for fiqh are Abu Bakr Siddiq, Umar ibn Khattab, Uthman ibn Affan, Ali ibn Abu Talib, Abdullah ibn Mas'ud, Abdullah ibn Umar, Abdullah ibn Abbas, Abdullah ibn Amr ibn Oss, Zayd ibn Thabit, may God bless him and grant him peace. and they cite our mother Aisha as an example.

Our Prophet Muhammad, may God bless him and grant him peace, sent his representatives from the learned Companions to teach Muslims in distant lands the rules of Sharia and to solve new issues that arise in their lives. For example, they sent Muaz ibn Jabal, may God bless him and grant him peace, to Yemen.

In the second half of the first and second centuries of the Hijri, the religion of Islam spread widely throughout the world. Various non-Arab peoples also became Muslims. Naturally, they did not have the opportunity to extract the sharia rules from the Holy Qur'an and the Sunnah of our Prophet Muhammad, may

God bless him and grant him peace. On the one hand, they do not know the language, and on the other hand, they have no knowledge. What to do? Of course, you should ask those who know. Thus, gradually, people started to emerge who would teach people religious rulings and answer their questions. Later, the situation demanded to write whole books and summarize the issues.

Gradually, in different parts of the Islamic world, scholars of jurisprudence began to grow. These scholars used four things as the main sources for their jurisprudence in their scientific work..

The first: the Holy Qur'an. That is, if a jurist wants to know the ruling of something in Islam, he first turns to the Holy Qur'an. Whatever judgment he has, he accepts without any hesitation.

The second: the Sunnah of the Messenger of Allah, may God bless him and grant him peace. If a jurist cannot find the answer to something in the Holy Qur'an, he turns to the Sunnah. He finds him and declares his verdict.

The third: Ijma is the unanimous acceptance of an issue by scholars who are ijtiha scholars of the same era. For example, the need to convert the Holy Qur'an into a book is not emphasized in the Qur'an itself or in the Sunnah of the Prophet, may God bless him and grant him peace. However, after the death of the Messenger of Allah, peace and blessings be upon him, he was worried that many reciters of the Holy Qur'an were martyred in the wars, and with the suggestions of Hazrat Umar, Caliph Abu Bakr Siddiq ordered the compilation of the Qur'an. Everyone agreed, no one objected. This work was done through "ijma".

Fourth: Comparison. That is, judging a matter that has not been ruled on in the previous sources, by comparing it with something that has a ruling on it in the current sources. For example, in the Qur'an, khamr, that is, an intoxicating drink obtained by fermenting things such as grapes, barley, honey, dates, etc., is forbidden. The scholars compared it to this and said that intoxicating drinks other than them are haram. The jurists presented many judgments to the public with the help of these evidences.

Conclusion. In conclusion, it should be said that the history of the Hanafi sect has a very interesting history. Some of them began to spread to different regions. But even though their knowledge was sometimes developed on a scientific basis, under the influence of a number of factors, it did not have the opportunity to penetrate among the people on a large scale, and gradually gave its place to the schools of Hanafi, Maliki and Shafi'i. released and left the field of action. In the end, the four schools of jurisprudence, Hanafi, Maliki, Shafi'i, and

Hanbali, which retained their status, are still gaining popularity in the Islamic world and satisfying the needs of Muslims.

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